

Blue-Action Deliverable D6.4

About this document

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Lead authors

Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut (DMI): Steffen M. Olsen (*)

SAMS Research Services Ltd (SRSL): Hannah Grist

University Bergen (UIB): Marius Årthun, Tor Eldevik (*)

Norwegian Research Center (NORCE): Svein Østerhus

Faroese Marine Research Institute (HAV): Karin M. H. Larsen, Bogi Hansen (*)

Konsortium Deutsche Meeresforschung e.V. (KDM) Jan-Stefan Fritz (*)

MEOPAR Incorporated (MEOPAR) Brad deYoung (*)

Scottish Association for Marine Science (SAMS): Stuart A. Cunningham (*)

National University of Ireland Maynooth (NUIM): Gerard McCarthy

(*) These are partners in AtlantOS and Blue-Action.

Reviewer

Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut (DMI): Chiara Bearzotti

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Summary for publication

In this deliverable we summarise **how the results achieved so far in Blue-Action have been feeding into the “BluePrint visions for an integrated Atlantic Ocean observing system in 2030”, into the AtlantOS Program and more broadly have provided inputs to the definition of the future Atlantic monitoring system.**

The All-Atlantic Ocean Observing System (AtlantOS) is an integrated concept for a forward-looking framework and basin-scale partnership to establish a comprehensive ocean observing system for the Atlantic Ocean as a whole. Recently, at OceanObs’ 2019, it has been presented how the H2020-funded project AtlantOS is planned to become a larger Program, building on the coordinated work of the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) and the Group on Earth Observations (GEO). The strategy underlying the Program was recently published in a paper entitled “BluePrint visions for an integrated Atlantic Ocean observing system in 2030”.

Work carried out

The AtlantOS BluePrint for Ocean Observing in the Atlantic

The All-Atlantic Ocean Observing System (AtlantOS) is an integrated concept for a forward-looking framework and basin-scale partnership to establish a comprehensive ocean observing system for the Atlantic Ocean as a whole.

AtlantOS as a H2020-funded project was originally set up with the goal of bringing together the observing communities and countries of the Atlantic basin, providing the opportunity to join and support the system. For pursuing these tasks in the long-term, **the**

AtlantOS project will turn in a long-term AtlantOS Program, building on the coordinated work of the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) and the Group on Earth Observations (GEO), two international bodies that support and coordinate global ocean observing, complementing them and offering a new approach to organizing ocean observing at the basin-scale.

The **BluePrint visions for an integrated Atlantic Ocean observing system in 2030** (short BluePrint) has been published on 26 July 2019 (doi: 10.3389/fmars.2019.00428). The BluePrint was presented at the Ocean Obs’19 meeting on 16 – 20 September 2019 in Honolulu.

Blue-Action team members who are members of the BluePrint Core Group are Brad deYoung (MEOPAR) and Jan-Stefan Fritz (KDM). Brad deYoung led the process and was the primary author with all coauthors substantially contributing to the document. The BluePrint was reviewed by Gerard MacCarthy (NUIM) and relied on the contribution of other Blue-Action team members actively involved in AtlantOS: Karin M. Larsen (HAV), Stuart Cunningham (SAMS), Steffen Olsen (DMI).

Blue-Action contributes to the Vision for an All-Atlantic Ocean Observing System (BluePrint)

The BluePrint of the AtlantOS Program is a document which relies on the work and inputs provided by several authors across different institutions and affiliated to several projects and initiatives. Blue-Action is one of them.

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Blue-Action aims to improve our ability to describe, model, and predict Arctic climate change and its impact on Northern Hemisphere climate, weather, and their extremes, and to deliver valuated climate services of societal benefit.

The North Atlantic Ocean has a significant influence on Europe's weather and climate. This is related to the sea surface temperature and heat transported by ocean currents. Recent research suggests that we could use our understanding of the North Atlantic Ocean to predict winter temperatures in Europe and Arctic sea ice extent 5-10 years in advance.

To improve predictions of weather and climate in the future, and to better understand how climate change could affect Europe, we must continue to pursue trans-national research that links oceanography, climate and atmospheric sciences. Early-warning indicators for approaching climate impacts, fit-for-purpose ocean observing systems, and development of mitigation strategies should be prioritised. Investments in ocean and atmospheric sciences are essential to Europe's global leadership in weather and climate science and for safeguarding regions and communities from the risks posed by a changing climate.

Blue-Action contributes to defining the future Atlantic monitoring system

Essentially, Blue-Action is contributing to defining the future Atlantic monitoring system by:

1. Optimizing the **monitoring systems** at the gateways to the Arctic.
2. Assessing and enhancing the usefulness of the North Atlantic ocean observations in decadal **prediction systems**.
3. Demonstrating the value of initialized decadal predictions in **climate services**.

The Monitoring System

Warm water enters the Arctic mainly from the Atlantic across the Greenland-Scotland Ridge and with a small contribution from the Pacific via the Bering Strait (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Warm ocean currents entering the Arctic Ocean. Credits: Gerard McCarthy (NUIM).

This warm, low latitude water can have a large impact on the Arctic, the effect of the inflows being described as **the 'Atlantification' and 'Pacification' of the Arctic**. In particular, the Barents Sea has been affected by Atlantification in recent years, with profound impacts on the sea ice. Warm Atlantic water enters the Arctic in three branches, mainly east of Iceland (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Average Atlantic water transport. Credits: Bogi Hansen (adapted from Osterhus et al. 2019, Arctic Mediterranean exchanges: a consistent volume budget and trends in transports from two decades of observations).

These locations have been monitored since the 1990s. Blue-Action is working on optimising the monitoring systems there, working with new techniques and technology to sustain these vital observations.

The Prediction System

Temperature changes in the Gulf Stream propagate slowly northwards – from the east coast of the USA to the west coast of Norway and toward the Arctic (Fig. 3) – spending up to ten years on the journey. Observations show that there exists a robust statistical relation between these poleward propagating ocean temperature anomalies and north-western European and Arctic climate variability.

Figure 3: Dominant ocean and atmosphere circulation in the North Atlantic sector. Credits: Marius Årthun (adapted from Årthun, Marius, et al. "Skillful prediction of northern climate provided by the ocean." Nature communications 8 (2017): 15875).

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Blue-Action is working on predicting northern climate up to a decade in advance, based on upstream ocean conditions (Fig. 4).

Figure 4 Predicted and observed climate. Credits: Marius Årthun (adapted from Årthun, Marius, et al. "Skillful prediction of northern climate provided by the ocean." *Nature communications* 8 (2017): 15875).

The Climate Services

Blue-Action builds on the results delivered by its monitoring and prediction components to develop innovative and valued climate services.

The five case-studies each incorporate small- and medium-sized enterprises or governmental organisations into a co-development framework to produce new climate services whose value is quantified. The focus areas are:

- **Winter tourism centers in Northern Finland**, developing seasonal time-scale forecasts of snow-making conditions for use by Rukakeskus ski resort.
- **Temperature-related human mortality in European regions**, developing forecasts and early-warning systems of heatwave events that can be used by public health authorities.
- **Extreme weather risks to maritime activities**, developing probabilistic forecasts of polar lows for incorporation into risk-management tools currently used by shipping insurance companies.
- **Climate services for marine fisheries**, developing seasonal-to-decadal forecasts of the distribution of marine fish species to aid management and planning in the fisheries sector.
- **Yamal 2040: Scenarios for the Russian Arctic**, linking climate knowledge and projections into the community driven production of development scenarios for the Yamal autonomous region.

Blue-Action contribution to the AtlantOS Program Meeting 2019

The first meeting to present the new AtlantOS Program was held at OceanObs'19 on 15 September 2019, Honolulu, Hawaii. At the meeting, Brad deYoung presented the AtlantOS Program concept, the BluePrint and the underlying research activities, and the ways forward in the implementation of the Program (¹). About 40 participants from countries around the Atlantic and key programs/organizations and the European Commission (EC/DG RTD) joined the meeting. Blue-Action was represented by the coordinator, Steffen M. Olsen (DMI).

Additional Blue-Action contributions to the AtlantOS project and Program

A number of white papers presented at OceanObs'2019 highlighted the Blue-Action contributions to the BluePrint, relying on the research work implemented by Blue-Action scientists.

- 31: Synthesizing continuous observations of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation
- 80: Experience of observing the Atlantic gained from 15 years of the RAPID programme
- 191: Meridional Heat Transport (MHT) from Space: The Importance of Synergy of Satellite and In Situ Measurements
- 55: A BluePrint for an Integrated Atlantic Ocean Observation System
- 82: Implementation of an Atlantic Ocean Observation System
- 93: The decade long Brazilian efforts to observe and describe the air-sea interaction processes in the South Atlantic and the Southern Ocean
- 193: The Atlantic Meridional Transect
- 245: Climate Linked Atlantic Sector Science CLASS

In Blue-Action, Stuart Cunningham (SAMS) was involved in two papers, acknowledging Blue-Action, which were a merger a number of abstracts at OceanObs:

- Frajka-Williams, E., Ansorge, I. J., Baehr, J., Bryden, H. L., Chidichimo, M. P., Cunningham, S. A., et al. (2019). Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation: Observed Transport and Variability. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 6, 3559–18. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00260>
- Cunningham St. and many Blue-Action and AtlantOS authors “Pole-to-Pole In-Situ Observing Systems for Measuring 1 Volume, Heat and Freshwater 2 Fluxes of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation”, submitted for review to *Reviews of Geophysics*.

Marie Porter (SAMS) who is collaborating with Stuart Cunningham (SAMS) in Blue-Action, but is part of the H2020 AtlantOS project for glider observations in the European Slope Current, presented also a poster at OceanObs on “Gliders for monitoring boundary currents”.

Marie has also provided valid contributions to the and have contributed to the deliverable D6.3 “Blue-Action, the A4 Project and ATLAS Joint Workshop on Subpolar North Atlantic Eastern Boundary”, held on 14 October 2019 in Edinburgh (UK).

Main results achieved

We are glad that part of the Blue-Action team could contribute actively to the concepts underlying the BluePrint.

Impact

The work presented in this deliverable contributes to the following expected impact of Blue-Action:

¹ More details about the Program can be found here: www.AtlantOS-ocean.org

Improving innovation capacity and the integration of new knowledge

By transferring knowledge from one project/program to the others.

Lessons learned and Links built

We are glad that the inputs provided could be discussed with the authors of the Blueprint and were flagged at the meeting held at OceanObs'2019.

Contribution to the top level objectives of Blue-Action

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of all the objectives and specific goals indicated in the Description of the Action, part B, Section 1.1: <http://blue-action.eu/index.php?id=4019>

- Objective 1 Improving long range forecast skill for hazardous weather and climate events
- Objective 2 Enhancing the predictive capacity beyond seasons in the Arctic and the Northern Hemisphere
- Objective 3 Quantifying the impact of recent rapid changes in the Arctic on Northern Hemisphere climate and weather extremes
- Objective 4 Improving the description of key processes controlling the impact of the polar amplification of global warming in prediction systems
- Objective 5 Optimizing observational systems for predictions
- Objective 6 Reducing and evaluating the uncertainty in prediction systems
- Objective 7 Fostering the capacity of key stakeholders to adapt and respond to climate change and boosting their economic growth
- Objective 8 Transferring knowledge to a wide range of interested key stakeholders

References (Bibliography)

- Årthun, Marius, et al. "Skillful prediction of northern climate provided by the ocean." *Nature communications* 8 (2017): 15875
- Osterhus et al. 2019, Arctic Mediterranean exchanges: a consistent volume budget and trends in transports from two decades of observations

Dissemination and exploitation of Blue-Action results

Dissemination activities

The contents of this deliverable have been disseminated at OceanObs'2019 and meetings with AtlantOS.

Type of dissemination activity	Name of the scientist (institution), title of the presentation, event	Place and date of the event	Type of Audience	Estimated number of persons reached	Link to Zenodo upload
Others (Poster)	Steffen Olsen (DMI) et al. poster on "Predicting the North Atlantic for Climate Services" at OceanObs'2019	Honolulu (US), 16 September 2019	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	600	https://zenodo.org/record/3529759

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Participation to a workshop	Steffen M. Olsen (DMI), Workshop on the AtlantOS Program at OceanObs'19	Honolulu (US), 15 September 2019	Scientific Community (higher education, Research), , Policy makers	40	N/A
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Uptake by the targeted audiences

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is the general public (PU) is and is made available to the world via [CORDIS](#).